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Carbon abundance determination at metal-poor regime

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Abstract

Carbon, one of the most abundant element in the universe, is easily investigated in the stellar photosphere. In the spectra of late type stars, absorption atomic lines are investigated to derive C abundance. Unfortunately, these lines are too weak at metal-poor regime and C-bearing molecular lines are used to derive carbon abundance. We here compare C abundance derived from atomic lines and molecular (CH, C₂ and CN) lines in few metal-poor stars and the ultra iron-poor star HE 0107–5240.

1 Introduction

Carbon is one of the most abundant elements in the universe. It is one of the essential ingredients for life, as we know it, but C also plays a fundamental role in star formation at ultra and extremely metal-poor (EMP) regime: ionised carbon and neutral oxygen are efficient agents for cooling the gas while compressing to form low-mass ($M < M_{\odot}$) stars (Bromm & Loeb 2003). This efficient process to form low-mass EMP stars is observationally confirmed by the increasing number of carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars with respect to C-normal stars decreasing $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Frebel et al. (2007) introduced a ‘transition discriminant’, which takes into account C and O abundance, to asses the minimum amount of these two elements to form a low-mass star. Below this threshold, we know that low-mass stars do form anyway (see Caffau et al. 2024; Limberg et al. 2025), they use dust as cooling agent (see e.g. Schneider et al. 2012) or they form through fragmentation (see e.g. Clark et al. 2011). It is then of paramount importance to be able to derive C abundance in all metallicity regimes and especially for low $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ stars. It is also important to verify if the molecular bands we use to derive A(C) introduce any systematic in the C abundance determination.

Atomic C I lines are investigated in the solar photosphere, but these lines become very often (depending on the stellar parameters) too weak at metal-poor regime to be investigated. On top of that, the strongest C I lines fall in the infrared wavelength range, which is contaminated by telluric absorption and it is less investigated than the optical wavelength range at high resolution. The G-band (~ 428 nm) is usually analysed at metal-poor regime, but for some CEMP stars also the Swan band of C₂ lines in the region of the Mg Ib is well detectable as the

CN band at 388 nm. We here compare the carbon abundance derived from the G-band and few infrared atomic lines in few metal-poor stars. We also investigate the four above mentioned C tracers in the ultra iron-poor star HE 0107–5240 (Christlieb et al. 2002).

2 Carbon abundance determination

In the UVES 760 setting, few C I atomic line, strong in the solar spectrum, are still detectable in the spectra of some metal-poor stars and, when clean from telluric absorption, they are available to derive $A(C)$. In few UVES spectra we investigated the clean C I lines at 833.5147, 872.7139 and 911.1799 nm. There are also atomic lines at 906.1432 and 907.8278 nm, but they are always contaminated in the stellar spectra we investigated. These atomic C I lines are affected by departure from local thermodynamical equilibrium (LTE). For the C I 911 nm line in the solar case, depending on the S_H value adopted, the correction for non-local thermodynamical equilibrium (NLTE) is negative and about 0.2-0.3 dex (Caffau et al. 2010; Alexeeva & Mashonkina 2015). For the metal-poor stars investigated by Alexeeva & Mashonkina (2015), the NLTE corrections are smaller in absolute value than for the Sun, the lines are weaker at metal-poor regime. For three metal-poor stars observed with UVES (437+760) in the frame of the project ‘The Gaia RVS benchmark stars’ (Caffau et al. 2021), we investigated the C I lines at 833.5 and 872.7 nm. For the star HE 0107–5240, the C I line at 911 nm is weak but still visible in the UVES spectrum.

The G-band, formed by CH lines at around 430 nm, is widely investigated to derive carbon abundance. We are aware that effects due to hydrodynamical motion of the gas in the stellar photosphere (3D effects) influence the C abundance derived from the G-band (Gallagher et al. 2016, 2017). Hoppe et al. (2026) derived small 3D-NLTE effects in the solar photosphere.

RVS392 is a slightly metal-poor evolved star ($T_{\text{eff}} = 4098$ K, $\log g = 1.07$, $\xi = 1.41$ km s⁻¹ and $[Fe/H] = -0.88$). We derived from the C I line at 872.7 nm $A(C) = 7.77$ (the line at 833.5 nm had a strange shape but provide a consistent abundance of $A(C) = 7.85$), to be compared to $A(C) = 7.72$ derived from the G-band.

RVS617 is a metal-poor, evolved star ($T_{\text{eff}} = 4117$ K, $\log g = 0.77$, $\xi = 1.67$ km s⁻¹ and $[Fe/H] = -1.56$). The C I atomic lines free from telluric contamination are really weak. From the very weak 872.7 nm line we derived $A(C) = 6.64$, to be compared to the value derived from the of $A(C) = 6.56$.

RVS638 is also a metal-poor evolved star ($T_{\text{eff}} = 4290$ K, $\log g = 1.44$, $\xi = 1.49$ km s⁻¹ and $[Fe/H] = -1.09$). $A(C) = 7.42$ from the weak 872.7 nm line (the other atomic lines are affected by telluric contamination) is in good agreement with the carbon abundance ($A(C) = 7.35$) derived from the G-band.

HE 0107–5240 is an ultra iron-poor star with a strong enhancement in carbon, nitrogen and oxygen (Christlieb et al. 2002; Caffau et al. 2025). In 12 OBs of the UVES observations, the C I at 911.1 nm is weak but still visible. Unfortunately, the combined spectrum is noisy and the derived abundance ($A(C) \approx 6.6$) is uncertain, depending also on how the combination of the OBs is done (see Fig. 1 upper panel). Anyway, this value is not far from $A(C) \approx 6.72$ derived from the G-band. Carbon abundance derived from the C₂ band (the Swan band) at 515 nm is larger (see Fig. 1 middle panel) and even larger the value derived from the CN band at 388 nm (see Fig. 1 lower panel), assuming $A(N) = 4.42$ from the NH band at 336 nm.

Figure 1: For HE0107-5240, the best fit (solid red) compared to the observed spectrum (solid black): upper panel the 911.17 nm C I line, middle panel the C_2 Swan band and lower panel the CN band at 388 nm.

3 Conclusions

Carbon abundances, in the few metal-poor stars here investigated, derived from the G-band and atomic C I lines are consistent in the analysis done under 1D-LTE assumption. For HE 0107–5240, A(C) derived from the C₂ and CN bands provide a much larger value.

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